

SHORT COMMUNICATIONS

Chemical Investigation of the bark of *Delonix regia* (Boj) Raf

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Lupeol and β -sitosterol have been isolated from the alcoholic extract of the bark of *D. regia*.

Delonix regia (Leguminosae)¹ is a big tree commonly known as Raktachura in Bengal. It is planted in avenues and gardens in all the warmer and damper parts of India. Since no work on this plant is reported in literature, a chemical investigation of the bark of the plant was undertaken.

The alcoholic extract of the bark of *D. regia*, that showed negative test for alkaloids was separated into neutral and acidic fractions. The acidic fraction did not yield any crystalline material even after esterification with diazomethane followed by chromatography. The neutral fraction on chromatography over activated alumina first provided lupeol, identified as its acetate by mixed melting point with an authentic sample. The second solid from the column on acetylation and crystallization furnished a crystalline compound identified as β -sitosterol acetate by mixed melting point with an authentic specimen.

EXPERIMENTAL

Dried and powdered bark of *D. regia* (1 kg). was extracted with alcohol in a Soxhlet for 8 hrs. The brown gummy residue (8.2 g.) obtained on removal of solvent showed negative test for alkaloids with Dragendorff's reagent. It was taken up in ether and washed with 5% aqueous potassium hydroxide solution (200 ml.). The alkaline solution on acidification yielded a gummy material, which on esterification with diazomethane followed by chromatography did not yield any crystalline material.

Lupeol Acetate: The above ether layer was washed with cold water till neutral. The neutral ether soluble part (4.96 g.) was chromatographed over a column of activated alumina (100 g.). Elution with a mixture of petroleum ether and benzene (2:3), furnished a solid (0.31 g.), m. p. 185-205°, which was acetylated with acetic anhydride (2.3 ml.) and pyridine (2.3 ml.). The acetylated product (0.25 g.) on several crystallizations from a mixture of chloroform and methanol furnished lupeol acetate, m. p. 208-211° (lit², m. p. 218°), identical (mixed melting point) with an authentic specimen of lupeol acetate. (Found: C, 81.97; H, 11.09. Calc. for C₃₂H₅₂O₂; C, 81.99; H, 11.18%).

β -Sitosterol Acetate: On further elution of the column with a mixture of benzene and ether (2:3), a gummy solid (0.07 g.), m. p. 124-126° was obtained. On acetylation with

1. The Wealth of India, Raw Materials, Vol. III, 1952, Council of Scientific and Industrial Research, New Delhi, p. 30.
2. Elsevier's Encyclopaedia of Organic Chemistry, Ed. E. Josephy and F. Radt, Vol. 14, 1940, p. 577.

acetic anhydride (1 ml) and pyridine (1 ml.), it yielded a product (0.045 g). m.p. 115-119°, which on several crystallizations from a mixture of chloroform and methanol furnished β -sitosterol acetate, m.p. 123-126° (lit³, m.p. 127-128°), which was identical (mixed melting point) with an authentic specimen of β -sitosterol acetate. (Found: C, 81.48; H, 11.23. Calc. for $C_{31}H_{52}O_2$: C, 81.52; H, 11.48%).

The authors are indebted to the Council of Scientific and Industrial Research, New Delhi for the award of a Junior Research Fellowship to one of them (S.R.).

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Received, February 23, 1968.